

RESEARCH ARTICLE

EFFECT OF PALM BUNCH, SORGHUM SPIKE AND MAIZE COB ASHES ON ROOT GROWTH AND POTASSIUM STATUS OF CASSAVA

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ABSTRACT

The paper examines the effect of different sources of Organic manure as key nutrient (Potassium) on tuber yield of Cassava (Manihot esculenta Crantz). Ashes obtained from Empty Fresh Bunches (EFB) of oil palm, Maize Cobs (MC), and Sorghum Spikes (SS) were subjected to chemical analyses in the laboratory and discovered to contain high percentage of potassium nutrient. EFB Ash had the highest percentage of K, when compared with Ash of MC and SS. These organic K supplements were applied in different combinations using NPKF as control in an experiment conducted on a sandy loam soil in Ilorin to determine the best treatment that will supply high amount of potassium needed for cassava production. Results indicate that applying Ash of EFB two months after planting gave the highest root yield per plot, among the sole organic treatments applications. Also the treatment of EFB+MC+SS gave optimum yield of cassava root better than EFB treatment. However, the combination of EFB+MC+SS+NPKF was significantly different (5%) among all treatments, an indication that Potassium is highly responsible for root development. Laboratory analysis also showed that the ash of EFB was significantly different from all other ash sources in terms of K nutrient present. Thus, the EFB+MC+SS treatment was recommended as a soil amendment for organically cultivated cassava. A combination of at least two of the organic manure with NPKF was also suggested for optimum crop yield, soil pH control and improved soil fertility.

KEYWORDS: *Cassava, Potassium, Organic Manure, Fertilizer, Yield, Soil fertility*

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INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is at present the largest producer of cassava in the world and also the largest consumer of the by-products, as a result there is need for increase in cassava production in Nigeria. The annual yield production per hectare increased in 1978 from 12 to 33 million t/ha, ranking Nigeria first in the world. The total harvested crop in 2003 was 21 million hectares with an average yield of about 11t/ha. In 2006, its total production was about 34 million metric tonnes per hectare. In Nigeria, cassava production is far the largest in the world, a third more than production in Brazil and almost double the production in Indonesia and Thailand (FAO, 2002).

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) adjust its rate of growth to the nutrient supplying ability of the soil, maintaining a level of productivity that can be sustained by the nutrient supplying power of the soil (Fulton, 1996) as the fertility of the soil affects the yield levels obtained (Howler, 1985).Tuber crops, which have high potassium (K) requirements, are grown mostly in lateritic (Ultisols and Oxisols), red (Alfisols) and sandy loam soils (Entisols), which are poor in native fertility, nutrient retention, and ironically in K supplying power as well.

Tuber crops, in general and cassava in particular, are mainly grown for their starch. It is well known that K plays a significant role in the synthesis and translocation of carbohydrates, and as a catalyst for activating a number of enzymes involved in the synthesis of starch, protein and glycosides. Potassium has a moderating effect on improving the tuber quality by increasing the starch content and reducing the cyanogenic glycosides responsible for bitterness in cassava. Nair and Sadanandan (1987) studied the effect of graded levels of K application and observed that K nutrition profoundly influences the number of storage roots and mean tuber weight per plant. An increase in the number of tubers per plant and tuber size was observed with an increase in K₂O application rates up to 200kg/ha.

In Asia, Latin, American, Nigeria and other African countries in the sub-Sahara, significant positive responses of cassava to N, P, and K fertilizers have been recorded (Agbaje and Akinlosotu, 2004; Nair *et al.*, 1988; FAO, 1980).A long-term fertilizer experiment showed that continuous cultivation of cassava with only N or P fertilizers reduced the tuber yield (Susan John *et al.*, 2005). On average, the yield declines were up to 71% in the N only treatment and 83% in the P only treatment. Phosphorus application in the absence of K application has a negative effect on the crop because high yields in the first crop might have exhausted the available soil K supply. However, the yield reduction (63%) was comparatively less in the K only treatment. This might be because a major portion of the K uptake (about two-third) gets exported to tuberous roots (Susan John *et al.*, 2005).

Ash generally has good acid neutralizing capacity and ability to supply the soil with bases (Ca²⁺, K⁺, P, Mg²⁺, Na²⁺); and this depends on the content of oxides, hydroxides and carbonates of Ca, Mg, K, and P. It has been stated that ash can be used to counteract natural and anthropogenic acidification of soil and loss of nutrients (Serafinelion, 2002; Eriksson, 1998). Ash, especially wood ash, reactivate physical, chemical and biological properties of arable soils that have previously been damaged as a result of inappropriate handling, unfavorable climate conditions as well as continuous cropping, over usage of land and persistent use of NPK fertilizer (Ojeniyi, 2002; Abyhammar *et al.*, 1994). Martikainen (2002) reported an ash induced pH increase of 0.6 – 1.0 pH units in humus soil. Nwite *et al.*, (2009), reported that essential plant nutrient such as exchangeable

K, and Ca, including fertility index as the CEC, and available phosphorus were statistically improved by the application of ashes (wood, leaf and rice husk ashes) in an Ultisol of Ishiagu.

There are various studies reporting the high yield in crops subjected to ash of palm bunch. Ojeniyi *et al.*, (2009) reported high root yield with the use of oil palm bunch ash in cassava production. Safo *et al.*, (1997) found that palm bunch ash increased yield of cowpea as well as increased soil pH, available P and effective cation exchange capacity of Ghanaian soil. Ahaiwe (2008) asserted from his study on performance of palm bunch ash on ginger that highest plant height, highest average leaves number and highest yield was obtained in the plot treated with 600g of palm bunch ash. Ojeniyi *et al.*, (2006) found that oil palm bunch ash at 4tons/ha increased significantly yield of maize and its leaf N, P, K, Ca and Mg content.

It is an established fact that inorganic fertilizers are scarce in supply, expensive and have negative impact on the environment. Consequently, organic farming has been advocated over the years and farmers are being encouraged to adopt the strategy because it is cheaper, readily available and environment friendly, with good optimum yield. Thus, the study aimed at evaluating the different ash sources so as to ascertain the best ash that will give high yield of cassava tuber as well as improve the soil's engineering, physical and chemical properties on a selected field, in Kwara State.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The study was carried out at the Research Farm of the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization, Ilorin, Nigeria (Longitude 4°, 30' East and Latitude 8°, 26' North). The soil textural class was a Sandy loam soil. Samples were collected from all considerable organic materials (ash) and chemical analysis were conducted to determine the percentage proportion of Sodium (Na^{2+}), Calcium (Ca^{2+}) and Potassium (K^+).

The experimental design adopted for the study was Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with six (6) treatments and four (4) replications each. The six (6) treatments consist of; (i) EFB (ii) MC (iii) SS (iv) EFB+MC+SS (v) NPK 15:15:15 Fertilizer (Control) (vi) EFB+MC+SS+NPKF on each plot. The treatments were imposed two (2) months after planting (MAP). Cassava variety selected for the experiment was TS419 and application rate of the various treatments above are at the following levels; 2.5t/ha, 2.5t/ha, 2.5t/ha, (755+755+755) kg/ha, 600kg/ha, (567+567+567+150) kg/ha respectively.

Plot size was 2000m² (50m x 40m). The land was cleared, ploughed, harrowed and ridged. Cassava cuttings (20cm long) were planted on the creep of ridges at 1m by 1m. Planting was done in April and June, 2013. Weeding was done at 2, 5 and 10 months after planting (MAP) by using traditional weed control measures.

Laboratory Methods

Soil samples were collected before tillage operation and prior to the month of harvesting, using Latin-Square Fashion method, to evaluate the engineering soil physical and chemical properties. The soil samples were air-dried and sieved with 2mm sieve. Soil fraction less than 2mm from each of the replicates were then analyzed using the following methods; soil moisture content was determined gravimetrically, bulk density was determined using core sampler, soil hydraulic conductivity was determined using the core permeameter, soil organic matter was determined

using Base Saturation method, soil texture was determined using textural class, soil acidity and alkalinity were determined using pH scale meter, total nitrogen was determined using Kjeldahl digestion and distillation method, available phosphorus was determined using spectrophotometer, calcium and Magnesium were determined using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Buck Scientific 210VGP), cation exchange capacity, potassium and sodium were determined using Flame Photometer (Buck Scientific PFP-7).

Organic Ash Analysis

Prior to land preparation, plant residues were collected and burnt to harvest their various ashes as organic manure, which were subjected to chemical analysis. Calcium (Ca^{2+}) was determined using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Buck Scientific 210VGP), while Potassium (K^+) and Sodium (Na^+) were determined using Flame Photometer (Buck Scientific PFP-7).

Leaf analysis

At harvest (12MAP), leaf samples were collected from each plot, air-dried and ground. Samples were air-dried for 48hr at 65°C in oven and ground to pass 0.5mm pore size. The samples were digested using Kjeldahl method, Molybdenum blue colorimetry and flame photometer for Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium respectively.

Root data

The mean root diameter, length and number of roots per plant were measured at 3, 6, 9 and 12 months after planting (MAP). Three plants were randomly selected and uprooted from each plot for measurements. Roots harvested were oven-dried at 65°C for 48hr and root weights taken.

Statistical analysis

Data were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using the SPSS statistical package and the means compared using the Least significant difference (LSD) at 5% probability level ($p < 0.05$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of different sources of ash on soil physical engineering properties

Chemical analyses of the ashes from various sources indicated the presence of considerable amounts of Na, K and Ca (Table 1). EFB had the highest percentage of chemical nutrient constituent, with 352mg/kg of K, 6.1mg/kg of Na and 210mg/kg of Ca respectively. This proportion is followed by MC (211mg/kg of K, 3.7mg/kg of Na and 46.9mg/kg of Ca) and SS (171mg/kg of K, 3mg/kg of Na and 40.80mg/kg of Ca) with the least chemical nutrient constituent (Fig. 1). The critical levels of pH and nutrients set for cassava were pH 5.2-7.0, 0.2% N, 7.3mg/kg available P_2O_5 , 0.14-1.20cmol/kg exchangeable K_2O , and 3-8cmol/kg exchangeable Mg (Howeler, 1991). The critical levels of organic matter for crop production in Nigeria ecological zones were 3.0%, and the value for exchangeable Ca was 2.2cmol/kg (Akinrinde and Obigbesan, 2000). Hence EFB+MC+SS and EFB+MC+SS+NPKF nutrients released improved the soil physiochemical nutrient availability for cassava production. There was an improvement in Ca from 1.7cmol/kg to 2.1cmol/kg and 2.3cmol/kg respectively as shown in Table 3. Also the engineering soil physical properties were improved with values varying across treatments (Table 2). Effects of Organic nutrient on engineering soil physical properties were differentiated with Duncan Multiple Range Test (Table 5).

The result in Table 5, showed that there was statistical significant difference on the soil hydraulic conductivity by Duncan multiple range test among treatment at 5% ($p < 0.05$). The EFB+MC+SS+NPKF treatment was highly significant on soil hydraulic conductivity than other treatments except the control (NPKF) which was more significant. Table 5 also indicates a negative implication on the soil bulk density and moisture content, an indication that the NPKF was most responsible for loosening of the soil bulkiness. NPKF quickly releases its nutrients to the soil and most of these will be lost through leaching. The organic ash treatments, on the other hand release its nutrient gradually, thereby retaining and improving the soil microbial activities, with a great soil improvement mechanism.

Effect of different sources of ash on soil physiochemical properties

The result in Table 3, showed that there was statistical significant difference at 5% ($p < 0.05$) among treatment on the soil pH. The result indicated that treatments EFB+MC+SS and EFB+MC+SS+NPKF significantly improved the soil pH higher than other treatments with highest mean of 6.5 and 6.4 respectively. The pH of the soil in all treated organic plots had increased positively, including the control, than their original status of the soil/plot. This increase in pH level could be attributed to the significant improvement in the exchangeable bases in the soil. This is in line with Markinkainen (2002), who observed an increase of 2pH unit after ash application.

Table 3, also indicated that the effect of the different sources of ash on the soil organic matter percentage was statistical difference among the treatments at 5% ($p < 0.05$). It indicated that the treatment EFB+MC+SS and EFB+MC+SS+NPKF significantly improved the soil organic matter higher than other treatments with highest mean of (3.10).

In addition, Table 3 showed that exchangeable bases (Ca^{2+} , k^+ and Mg^{2+}) were statistically improved by the application of the treatment at 5% level ($p < 0.05$). The result indicated that treatment EFB+MC+SS and EFB+MC+SS+NPKF highly improved exchangeable Mg, Ca and K when compared with their initial status.

Effect of different sources of ash on cassava biomass yield

The treatments; EFB+MC+SS+NPKF, EFB+MC+SS and NPKF increased the number of cassava root, as indicated in Fig. 5. There was an increase with EFB+MC+SS+NPKF relative to the control (NPKF), which was significant. The treatment of EFB+MC+SS tended to give the highest value (yield output) when compared with other organic source (OS) of cassava, while the combination of EFB+MC+SS+NPKF shows the highest value for cassava. The mean value of number of cassava root is plotted for the treatments: EFB, MC, SS, EFB+MC+SS, NPKF and EFB+MC+SS+NPKF (Fig. 3) and (Fig. 5).

Therefore EFB+MC+SS and EFB+MC+SS+NPKF had similar and highest mean values of number of cassava roots. Number of roots increased with time between 3MAP and 6MAP and it dropped between 9MAP and 12MAP. This agrees with the observation of Ekanayake (1993) that on bulking, several primary fibrous roots die and decay due to competition for available carbohydrate (Fig. 2).

The yield mean of diameter cassava roots was highly significant at the 0.05 level by EFB+MC+SS and EFB+MC+SS+NPKF treatments (Fig. 4). Also these two (2) treatments gave the highest yield

for bitter cassava. Similar observation was found in respect of number of roots. The linear pattern of diameter of cassava root expanding with time in line with the finding of Ekanayake (1993), who observed that the higher the translocation of carbohydrate to the roots the higher the cambial activity causing it to enlarge in size (Fig. 2).

Root length of cassava was increased by EFB, EFB+MC+SS and EFB+MC+SS+NPKF treatments (Fig.6) with a significant increase, compared to the control (NPKF). EFB was observed to give slightly better output compared to the control (NPKF), because there was increase in potassium concentrate on the treatment. However, there was a slight decline in root length from 9MAP to 12MAP. These findings agree with those of Maduakor (1991) and Ekanayake (1993) who reported that a fall in root length of cassava harvested at 80-90 days after planting. The fall was attributed to rapid storage root bulking (Fig.2).

Also (Fig.7) shows that dry root weight was increased by EFB+MC+SS, NPKF and EFB+MC+SS+NPKF treatments. These treatments gave the highest value for root dry matter weight of cassava respectively. Since the values recorded for the three treatments were similar, application of EFB+MC+SS and EFB+MC+SS+NPKF were recommended, relative to the control. The 2.5t/ha EFB+MC+SS is also recommended in organic cassava production, because cassava tuber yield was increased in close proportion to NPKF. And on the sole treatment applications, EFB had the highest yield in term of cassava dry matter weight, which was an indicator for high amount of K present (Ojeniyi *et al.*, 2009).

The contributory effect of K nutrient from the various ashes on cassava biomass yield was also seen to be significantly different at 0.05 levels by Duncan multiple range test (DMRT), as indicated on Table 4.

The mean values of leaf constituent N, P and K concentrations are shown by the graph in Fig.7. The leaf N, P and K increased with the presence of EFB treatment on EFB+MC+SS and EFB+MC+SS+NPKF, compared to the control (NPKF). As a result, the EFB+MC+SS+NPKF treatment increased these nutrients than the control (NPKF). Therefore it is confirmed that EFB was an effective source of these nutrients.

CONCLUSION

This study has shown that ash from organic substances such as Empty Fresh Palm Bunch, Maize Cob and Sorghum Spike, used individually or in varied combinations compared well with the NPK fertilizer used as the control in this experiment. They all positively affected soil properties such as moisture content, hydraulic conductivity and bulk density as well as crop parameters such as leaf content, root diameter, and dry matter weight.

EFB ash had the highest percentage of K, when compared with ash of MC and SS an indication that Potassium is highly responsible for root development. Oil palm bunch ash increased availability and uptake of N, P, and K by cassava resulting in significant increase in cassava root length, diameter and yield. It has also been seen to positively contribute to elevate other soil nutrient content such as Ca and Na. A combination of at least two of the organic manure with NPKF was also suggested for optimum crop yield, soil pH control and improved soil fertility.

It is an established fact that a large percentage of the country's crop producers are the rural poor farmers with limited access to farm inputs and funds. The possibilities of using alternative materials that ordinarily would have been considered as waste products is indeed very appropriate for Nigerian farming system and adoption of organic farming, in line with global trend, should be encouraged. A combination of at least two of the organic manure with NPKF was also suggested for optimum crop yield, soil pH control and improved soil fertility.

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Table1: Chemical Analysis of Ash from Three Organic Sources

Organic Source	Nutrient Composition	Value
Empty palm bunch	Potassium	352.00mg/kg
	Sodium	6.10mg/kg
	Calcium	210.00mg/kg
Maize cob	Potassium	211.00mg/kg
	Sodium	3.70mg/kg
	Calcium	46.90mg/kg
Sorghum spikes	Potassium	171.00mg/kg
	Sodium	3.00mg/kg
	Calcium	40.80mg/kg

Table2: Engineering Properties of the Study Site

Parameters	Treatment Plot	Before	After
Hydraulic conductivity (cm/s)	EFB	3.01×10^{-3}	2.35×10^{-4}
	MC	2.36×10^{-3}	2.11×10^{-4}
	SS	2.41×10^{-3}	2.46×10^{-3}
	EFB+MC+SS	2.79×10^{-3}	5.11×10^{-5}
	NPKF Control	2.83×10^{-3}	4.71×10^{-6}
	EFB+MC+SS+NPKF	2.94×10^{-3}	5.93×10^{-5}
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	EFB	1.72	1.41
	MC	1.89	1.64
	SS	1.62	1.56
	EFB+MC+SS	1.68	1.33
	NPKF Control	1.71	1.30
	EFB+MC+SS+NPKF	1.70	1.27
Moisture content (%)	EFB	7.58	11.32
	MC	7.89	10.87
	SS	8.48	11.00
	EFB+MC+SS	6.45	9.70
	NPKF Control	7.25	10.44
	EFB+MC+SS+NPKF	6.23	10.67

Table 3: Chemical and Physical Properties of soil

Treatments	Before	EFB	MC	SS	EFB+MC+SS	NPKF Control	EFB+MC+SS+NPKF
Parameters							
pH (H ₂ O)	5.40	6.00	5.90	5.90	6.50	6.00	6.40
Total N (%)	0.20	0.26	0.22	0.21	0.28	0.30	0.31
Organic matter (%)	2.40	2.90	2.60	2.50	3.10	3.00	3.10
Organic carbon (%)	0.37	1.16	0.98	0.56	2.19	2.14	2.23
Available P (mg/kg)	6.50	6.80	6.60	6.54	7.00	7.20	7.50
Ca ²⁺ (cmol/kg)	1.70	1.84	1.80	1.76	2.10	1.90	2.30
Mg ²⁺ (cmol/kg)	3.70	5.00	4.50	4.00	7.30	6.80	8.3
K ⁺ (cmol/kg)	0.17	0.29	0.26	0.19	0.35	0.41	0.39
Na ⁺ (cmol/kg)	0.40	0.400	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.60	0.47
Exchangeable acidity (%)	35.50	40.20	39.00	37.30	41.90	47.00	45.30
ECEC(cmol/kg)	4.20	6.50	6.00	5.40	7.90	7.50	8.40
Base saturation (%)	64.40	74.70	69.50	64.40	77.00	77.00	79.00
Sand (%)	65.00	63.00	65.00	68.00	60.00	62.00	60.00
Silt (%)	25.00	27.00	25.00	20.00	28.00	22.00	26.00
Clay (%)	10.00	10.00	10.00	12.00	12.00	16.00	14.00
Textural Class	Sandy Loam						

EFB = Empty Fresh Bunch, MC = Maize Comb, SS = Sorghum Spike, NPKF = Nitrogen, Phosphorous, Potassium Fertilizer.

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Table 4: Effects of Organic nutrient on cassava biomass yield

Parameter	Root Diameter	Number of root	Tuber length	Dry root matter weight	Leaf percentage of Nitrogen	Leaf percentage of Phosphorus	Leaf percentage of Potassium
Treatment							
Empty Fresh Bunch (EFB)	6.1ab	11c	10cd	4ab	2.8b	2.0b	3.5b
Maize Cob (MC)	5.6b	10b	7b	13.2b	2.6ab	1.8ab	3.2ab
Sorghum Spike (SS)	3.6a	9a	6a	10.0a	2.4a	1.6a	2.8a
EFB+MC+SS	9.6d	12de	12d	14.0c	3.1bc	2.3bc	3.8bc
NPKF Control	8.9de	15d	9c	13.0c	3.0bc	2.2bc	3.8bc
EFB+MC+SS+NPKF	10e	17e	14e	16.0d	4.0c	2.6c	4.0c
Std. Error	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.1

Mean on the same column followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 0.05 levels by Duncan multiple range test (DMRT)

Table 5: Effects of Organic nutrient on soil engineering properties

Treatment	Empty Fresh Bunch (EFB)		Maize Cob (MC)		Sorghum Spike (SS)		EFB+MC+SS		NPKF Control		EFB+MC+SS+NPKF		Std. Error
Parameter	Before	After	Before	After	Before	After	Before	After	Before	After	Before	After	
Hydraulic Conductivity	6.1a	6.7c	6.1a	6.4b	6.1a	6.2ab	6.1a	7.2cd	6.1a	7.9e	6.1a	7.5d	0.1
Bulk Density	11.3e	9.0c	11.3e	9.7d	11.3e	9.7d	11.3e	8.2ab	11.3e	8.7b	11.3e	7.3a	0.3
Moisture Content	18.0a	22.1c	18.0a	20.9bc	18.0a	20.4b	18.0a	26.1d	18.0a	25.5cd	18.0a	29.8e	0.6

Mean on the same row followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 0.05 levels by Duncan multiple range test (DMRT)

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Fig. 1: Comparison analysis of Organic manure

Fig. 2: A graph of cassava parameters at different growth stages

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Fig. 3: Graph of different treatments at different growth stages on cassava production

Fig. 4: Diameter of Cassava root

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Fig. 5: Number of cassava root

Fig. 6: Length of Cassava root

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Fig. 7: Graph of proportion of dry matter weight and percentage of leaf constituent.

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